

Identification of Focus Points and Framework in Trainer's Training

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Abstract

There are educational issues to ensure that knowledge and skills are transferred more easily to the students. In addition to the importance of psychological aspects, providing students with a suitable physical learning environment is extremely important for simulation -based educational activities, because students will associate tasks and actions with physical context, which will facilitate recall through environmental clues. This can be called “Settled Learning” depending on the principle of education. For this reason, educators need to develop learning environments in accordance with the knowledge and skills they are trying to give to their students and consider how to apply the established learning principle to increase the effectiveness of educational interventions. Effective learning environments are variable depending on students, context and objectives of educational efficiency. For example, age, level and number of students, learning outputs to be obtained, how students interact physically and psychologically to take part in the educational activity, are necessary and accessible to make the important aspects of simulation realistic and how to evaluate the learning is the issues that should be considered. Although it examines how people learn, including education psychology, teaching methods, teaching processes and individual differences in learning, it can be said that the aim is to understand how people learn and keep current information. The branch of this psychology includes not only early childhood and puberty learning process, but also social, emotional and cognitive processes that participate in learning throughout life. The field of educational psychology includes several other disciplines such as developmental psychology, behavioral psychology and cognitive psychology. In this article, different perspectives taken in the field of educational psychology, the issues of educational psychologists and focus points on this field are discussed.

Keywords: *Education Psychology, Student's Education, Trainer's Education, Principles of Education Psychology, Principles of the Trainer's Education*

1. Introduction

As in other fields of psychology, researchers within educational psychology tend to take different perspectives when considering a particular problem. These perspectives focus on specific factors that influence what a person learns, including learned behaviors, cognition, experiences, and more. This perspective suggests that all behaviors are learned through conditioning. Psychologists taking this perspective rely on operant conditioning principles to explain how learning occurs. For example, teachers can reward learning by giving students tokens that can be exchanged for desirable items such as candy or toys. The behavioral perspective works on the theory that students learn when they are rewarded for "good" behavior and punished for "bad" behavior. While such methods are useful in some situations, the behavioral approach has been criticized for not considering such things as attitudes, emotions, and intrinsic motivations for learning.

2. Developmental Perspective

This focuses on how children acquire new skills and knowledge as they develop. Jean Piaget's stages of cognitive development are an example of an important developmental theory that looks at how children grow intellectually. By understanding how children think at distinct stages of development, educational psychologists can better understand what children are capable of at each point of their growth. This can help educators create teaching methods and materials best suited to specific age groups. The cognitive approach has become much more common in recent years, taking precedence over other theories mainly because it explains how things like memories, beliefs, emotions, and motivations contribute to the learning process. This theory is the result of their own motivations, not because of external rewards.

Cognitive Psychology aims to understand how people think, learn, remember and process information. Taking a cognitive perspective, educational psychologists are interested in understanding how children are motivated to learn, how they remember what they have learned, and how they solve problems.

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a. Constructivist approach

One of the latest learning theories, this perspective focuses on how we actively construct our knowledge of the world. Constructivism tends to explain more the social and cultural influences that influence what we learn. Those who take the constructivist approach believe that what a person already knows has the greatest impact on how they learn added information. This means that new knowledge can only be added to and understood from existing knowledge. This perspective is supported by psychologist Lev , who proposes ideas such as proximal development and the teaching scaffold. He is greatly influenced by the work of Vygotsky .

b. Experience and forward perspective

This perspective emphasizes that a person's own life experiences affect their understanding of added information. This method is like the constructivist and cognitive perspectives in that it considers the student's experiences, thoughts, and feelings . This method allows them to find personal meaning in what they are learning rather than feeling that the information does not apply to them. Summarizes different perspectives on human behavior while looking at different topics in the field of educational psychology. Some of these include the behavioral perspective, the constructivist approach, and the experiential perspective.

3. Topics in Educational Psychology

From the materials that teachers use of students' individual needs, an educational psychologist will delve into these issues to better understand the learning process. Some of these topics include:

a. Educational Technology:

This topic, which means looking at how diverse types of technology can help students learn instructional design, is closely related to the other topics below.

b. Designing Learning Materials Special Education:

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While specific instruction includes helping students who may need curriculum development, helping students identified as gifted students, it is expected to include finding ways to identify students who may need extra help, develop programs for struggling students, and even create new learning methods. They are mentored by teachers, as many educational psychologists collaborate directly with schools. Others collaborate with teachers to try out new learning methods for their students and develop new course syllabuses. It is even possible to become a counselor directly helping students deal with learning barriers.

4. Issues Affecting Training Methods

In all these roles, it is possible to influence educational methods and help students learn in the way that suits them best. A bachelor's degree and master's degree are usually required for careers in this field, although a separate doctoral degree at a university or school administration may be required to become an educational psychologist. This reveals that it will be more productive for teachers to collaborate with experts in this profession within the education community. Working in school often to help students and teachers improve the learning experience is a separate study in terms of the importance of educator training. Other professionals in this field work in research to explore the learning process and evaluate programs designed to promote learning.

Educational Psychology is a relatively young subfield that has experienced tremendous growth in recent years. Psychology did not emerge as a separate science until the late 1800s, so earlier interest in educational psychology was largely nurtured by educational philosophers. Many philosophers considered Johann Herbart the father of educational psychology. He believed that Herbart 's interest in a subject sparked his interest in a subject. It is important that the issue of training the trainer, which has a tremendous impact on the learning outcome, is well understood and implemented by the teachers. Teachers should consider this when deciding which types of instruction are most appropriate.

Later, psychologist and philosopher William James made important contributions to the field. 1899 "Psychology and Teachers" is considered the first textbook on Educational Psychology. Around the same time, the French psychologist Alfred Binet was developing the famous IQ

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tests. Developmental delays and forming special education programs. In the United States, John Dewey had a significant impact on education. Dewey 's ideas were progressive; He believed that schools should focus on students rather than subjects. He advocated active learning, arguing that firsthand experience is an important part of the process. More recently, educational psychologist Benjamin Bloom developed an important taxonomy designed to categorize and describe different educational goals. The three high-level domains he described were cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor learning goals. Key figures Throughout history, several additional figures have played a key role in the development of educational psychology. Some of these well-known individuals include:

- a. *John Locke: Locke, Tabula an English philosopher who proposed the concept of rasa, or the idea that the mind is essentially a blank slate at birth.16 This means that knowledge is developed through experience and learning.*
- b. *Jean Piaget : A SWI SS psychologist, best known for his theory of cognitive development, Jean Piaget 's influence on educational psychology is still evident today.*
- c. *BF Skinner : Skinner was an American psychologist who introduced the concept of operant conditioning influencing behavioral perspectives. His research on reinforcement and punishment continues to play a key role in education.*

5. EPS Evaluation Process

EPS in supporting the legal review process has identified several tensions and professional dilemmas, from concerns over the redefinition of the EP's role as a gatekeeper to resources (Farrell et al., 2006). There is also the suggestion that writing legal advice might make more sense the time available for EPS to work as perceived. (Lyons , 1999). For example, it has been suggested that many EPSs work on joint problem-solving and collaborative work with schools at an individual, group, and system level to work in a consultation model (Wagner, 2000). However, Crane (2016) describes how there has been a growing demand for EHCP assessments . EPS includes all scientific data and literature, not just any educational method. (Napep , 2015 Educational Psychology Workforce Survey, 2015). Additionally, due to the current constrained financial conditions of many LAS , many EPS practices are currently focused on legal work

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rather than preventive advisory work (Lee and Woods , 2017). This encourages schools to view EP as a “gatekeeper,” meaning that participation in EP can lead a school to access additional funding and resources rather than using EP skills to develop action plans and interventions for children. While there are tensions in EPS regarding their role in providing psychological advice, an EP remains a significant role. Presumably, given their training and expertise in assessing the education of children and young people, their skill set is that both special education needs to have an open role to others that a child and a young person can have, to use it effectively and to meet the conditions needed to overcome these needs. provision is deemed necessary. However, it is suggested that a creative and innovative approach is required to make psychological advice meaningful and purposeful for others (Cameron and Monsen , 2005).

In recent years, there has been an increase in the curriculum associated with educational psychology (Thomas and Vaughan , 2004). Thomas (1992) shows how the first increases of support staff to the 1980s were due to informal recruitment, often parents who wanted to help in the classroom. However, it was noted that these individuals, who soon became part of the school staff, took on additional and important responsibilities, including providing support to children.

6. Development, Learning and Motivation

It has traditionally not been a matter of dispute that teachers should understand human development, learning, and motivation theory. Courses focusing on these topics have been standard in teacher preparation programs for at least a century (Berliner , 1993). Unfortunately, courses as currently taught are; rarely produces beyond a rudimentary understanding of its essential ingredients. Typically, their primary purpose is courses that cover as much theory and as much information as possible in the shortest amount of time. It is necessary, then, to examine what the relevance of such courses has been challenged recently (Anderson et al., 1995; Berliner , 1993; Hoy- Woolfolk , 2000; O'Donnell and Levin , 2001; Weinstein and Way , 2003). Indeed, recognizing the importance of such courses, educational psychology now must advocate for inclusion in teacher preparation programs (Anderson et al., 1995; Weinstein and Way , 2003). Suggestions for how courses in educational psychology could be more relevant

and useful are many and varied (see, for example , Anderson et al., 1995; Hoy- Woolfolk , 2000; Poulou , 2005; Renninger , 1996; Shuell , 1996). Although a beneficial and generally positive development, such changes did not remain unchallenged (Doyle and Carter, 1996). For example , according to Doyle & Carter (1996, p. 25), “It is not enough to claim that educational psychology can be taught more effectively.” Doyle and Carter continue to emphasize the need for educational psychology to contribute to teachers' "frames of action," or method training.

Educational psychology may have a role in teaching methods; however, it should not be considered that this represents the central contribution of educational psychology to teacher preparation and professionalisation. The type of knowledge that Doyle and Carter emphasize, though not trivial, is largely procedural and implicit in nature is therefore not ideal for the development of reflective engagement types that would lead to general and flexible principles. It is also debatable whether it is a necessary practice for today's professional educators. Instead, what is needed is motivation for students and their learning (development, cognition, motivation, etc.). In the light of this knowledge, it is a solid foundation with comprehensive and penetrating applications in the application of this knowledge through students' diagnosis and learning situations. But while the question remains, how to achieve this is another question. One approach commonly suggested in reform proposals for educational psychology involves the use of rich cases from educational settings to position and apply theoretical concepts taught in an educational psychology course (Anderson et al. 1995, Hoy- Woolfolk , 2000; Renninger , 1996). Another important device is the use of lectures by pre-service teachers as an opportunity to develop diagnostic skills (Renninger , 1996).

Also, in such a process they may be asked to develop and develop analytical skills not typically emphasized in teacher preparation programmes, both the above discussions and several recent research efforts suggest the emergence of a new field of knowledge in educational psychology. Although the topic of teacher learning has been the focus of some early work by educational psychologists who learned to teach more than a decade ago, educational psychologists tend not to focus on learning as a major field of study for teachers. It is only in the last decade that educational psychologists have turned their attention from the study of teachers' behavior to the study of teachers' thoughts, cognition, and knowledge. The work of Leinhardt and Putnam

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(teachers' networks of knowledge and scenario theory) and Lampert (on the role of teachers' understanding of the subject matter and the role of students' interpretation of what it means) are most notable. This literature, and the literature of other researchers on teacher thinking, has explored how teachers' thinking, planning, and decision-making are constrained by the world in which teachers' work and their work operate.

Using psychology to understand the teacher can connect with teachers in powerful ways. Such psychological windows also open new possibilities for metaphors, transforming teaching into teachers' thinking or psychological lenses for examining teaching, new ways of thinking about how to connect psychology to teacher education. Researchers examining teachers' thinking and knowledge typically used cross-sectional rather than longitudinal approaches and therefore did not examine teachers' learning or the evolution of teachers' thinking over time. More recently, educational psychologists and teacher educators have begun working together to conduct a longitudinal study of how teachers learn to teach. In addition, examining teachers' beliefs, including their understanding of knowledge, is another subject of study. While this research represents an ambitious new effort, the methods and findings may be useful to educational psychologists who wish to examine students' learning in their teacher education programme. By saying, "This is an example of how to improve graduate student experiences and improve outcomes for students and teachers in schools," Villarreal also reminds that just like teachers and other educators, school psychologists have faced many challenges in recent years, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic . . . Castro- Villarreal has made the behavioral and mental health concerns of the students he works with more frequent and more severe. Pre-existing academic gaps based on ethnicity and income have also widened during the pandemic . This is said to be due to communities having fewer opportunities and resources. Fortunately, the authors are seeing improvements in students and teachers.

7. Pedagogical Foundations of Pre-service Teachers and Practicing Teachers

The role of educational psychology in the 21st century should be to provide a research-based pedagogical foundation upon which prospective teachers and practicing teachers can draw, to develop the habits of mind necessary to enable all students to learn. Historically, the field of

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educational psychology has focused on studying and examining how people learn (Crowel , Podell , & Kaminsky , 1997). However, the work most associated with the field of educational psychology in the 20th century has been the development of tests and measures to determine students' capacities and abilities. Most of the work done by educational psychologists has focused on identifying overperformance in the population. As such, educational psychology has been largely viewed as irrelevant by classroom teachers.

The primary role of educational psychologists is to label students who are gifted or eligible for special funding and training by special educators. Beyond the introduction to human development and learning theories taught in one or two initial courses, educational psychology noted that classroom teachers contributed little to their understanding of learning variations among "average" gifted students or to their pedagogical decision-making processes. In fact, for more than half a century the field of educational psychology has focused on identification procedures, and this focus on quantitative assessment now permeates our social lives.

Consciousness and placing standardized tests at the forefront of social and political agendas are also sub-topics that need to be evaluated. Socio -political policies rely on the field of educational psychology to provide standardized tests of intelligence and aptitude that help identify and label individuals who do not do well in school. Recently, state proficiency test results have been used as a key component of "district scorecards" that describe "pass" and "fail" school systems in Ohio and other states. While many educators have expressed concern about using test results to permanently label children or determine the success of a school district, what is clear is that the work of twentieth-century educational psychologists has shaped it, reaching a level of proficiency in defining the face of education as we know it. However, identifying and tagging problems is only the first step in any problem-solving strategy. Educational psychology in the twenty-first century must take society beyond identifying learning problems to finding solutions; Consideration should also be given to choosing from a variety of teaching methods and implementing action plans that help students achieve their grade-level learning goals. It is seen as one of the results obtained because of literature reviews that it is time to function as analytical people. To do this, educators need a repertoire of assessment skills and content-appropriate teaching methods to guide teaching decisions. This pedagogical foundation must be integrated into each.

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The way the educator thinks about student learning and teaching, although it has been tried to be summarized in this article, is another issue that needs to be mentioned separately in terms of literature. These well-developed "habits of mind" must work on an intuitive level to direct a teacher's attention to identifying and responding to individual students' needs. It takes time to develop these habits of mind; time to understand the philosophical, theoretical and scientific foundations of sound content pedagogy; time to develop pedagogical skills themselves; and it is natural that the time to develop the expertise necessary to make sound pedagogical decisions based on the needs of particular students should be presented in the form of data as a result of these studies. These skills cannot be developed in one or more areas.

Two introductory courses for trainees should only be instilled throughout initial teacher education and continuing professional development. Educational psychologists can play a vital role in the development of this pedagogical foundation, bridging education in neuroscience, medicine, and psychology, and between theory, philosophy, and scientific research. While including the most up to date, it should not be overlooked that science provides information about how people learn in our educational psychology courses and in our field interactions, and helps us focus our research efforts on developing, evaluating, and disseminating their practical applications.

Interdisciplinary research findings will also contribute to the evaluation of data to provide sound pedagogical alternatives to future and practitioner teachers.

national research Council Committee on Developments in the most recent report of How People Learn (Bransford, JD, Brown, AL, Cocking, RR, 1999) published by Science of Learning highlights five new understandings of learning based on research done over the past 30 years. All five areas indicated represent a shift in the view of effective learning from practice and practice to understanding and practice.

These new understandings of learning require learning environments that are "student-centered, knowledge-centered, assessment-centered and community-centered". While it should be applicable to any content, recognizing the role played by prior knowledge in the learning process and understanding the importance of cultural contexts in learning should be evaluated in the same context. Educational psychologists have a responsibility to incorporate these

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research findings into teacher preparation, staff development, and field consultations. Educational psychology in the twenty-first century must focus on finding solutions to problems.

8. Problems Identified by the Field in the Last Century

linkages between disciplines have become vital to understanding how people learn, it is clear that education must function as a bridge to these other disciplines. Educational psychologists must go beyond the problem-finding role by reframing our behavior. It plays a role in teacher preparation and fieldwork to include all steps in the problem-solving model. The field of Educational Psychology has played a key role in shaping the focus of education over the past century. In the new millennium, it is necessary to continue to shape the focus of education by directing the efforts of our field and society beyond identifying problems to the research and dissemination of solutions.

Maslach and Leiter (1999), in their study model of teacher burnout, suggested that burnout leads to less participation in teaching, which may undermine students' participation in the classroom. Depersonalization captures an experience where teachers disconnect from students and develop negative attitudes towards them. Given the importance of positive teacher-student relationships for a range of school-related outcomes (for example, Gehlbach, Brinkworth, & Harris, 2012; Wentzel, 2010; Wubbels & Brekelmans, 2005), there is reason to speculate that teacher depersonalization may be particularly negative. It is no coincidence that the results for classroom behavior of both teachers and students are still valid today. Few studies have so far examined the consequences of burnout in terms of classroom experiences and behaviors of teachers and students. In a recent exception, Soenens et al. (2012) found that after controlling for each burnout dimension, depersonalization, not emotional exhaustion, predicted challenging and intrusive teacher behaviors in the classroom. In another study, Shen et al. (2015) found that teacher depersonalization, but reduced emotional exhaustion or personal accomplishment, was negatively associated with students' adaptive motivation to learn. Besides emphasizing the negative role of teacher depersonalization, these studies are consistent with the indirect link suggested by Maslach and Leiter (1999) that burnout affects teachers' classroom behavior,

which in turn will affect students. However, there is no study that evaluates this suggestion by examining the effects of teacher burnout on both teacher and student behaviors.

Studies have shown a strong positive relationship between teacher burnout and teacher reports of student misbehavior (BibouNakou , Stogiannidou , & Kiosseoglou , 1999; Blase , 1982; Brouwers & Tomic , 1999; Byrne , 1991; Fernet , Guay , Senécal , & Austin, 2012).). ; Friedman , 1995; McCormick and Barnett , 2011). The interpretation that students' destructive behaviors are a worthy cause and risk factor of burnout is logical, but teacher burnout, especially teachers' depersonalization of students, can also affect students' destructive behaviors. Given that students recognize teachers' symptoms of depersonalization (Evers , Tomic , & Brouwers , 2004), they may respond by not cooperating or interrupting the teacher's lectures.

9. Teacher Reports

Previous studies relied on teacher reports of both burnout and student disruptive behavior collected in a single session. For example, although there is an association between perceived principal support and depersonalization, it tends to be low (for example, Greenglass , Burke , and Konarski , 1997), implying that personal factors such as teachers' sources of motivation may be at least, if not more important. Autonomous motivation is a core concept in SDT (Ryan & Deci , 2017). In summary, people are autonomously motivated to perform tasks that they perceive to reflect core personal values and goals and which they bring to life with an intrinsic sense of choice and will (Ryan , Deci , Grolnick , & La Guardia , 2006). Autonomous motivation is reflected in the reasons why teachers participate in teaching. Thus, the concept of teacher enthusiasm refers to "what" the desensitizing teachers do and feel in the classroom, while the concept of autonomous motivation refers to the "why" teachers continue their teaching activities and, therefore, students are more or less likely to do. (See Deci & Ryan , 2000 for a broad discussion of the distinction between what and why behavior is). Years ago, Ryan and Connell (1989) suggested that autonomous motivation is reflected in individuals "determined" and "intrinsic" reasons (or motives) for behavior. When they perform an activity for specified reasons, individuals do so because they embrace the value of the activity and recognize its importance to them.

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If there are internal reasons for their behavior, individuals do so because they derive internal satisfaction and enjoyment from the activity. In a study by Roth , Assor , KanatMaymon , and Kaplan (2007) on identified and intrinsic reasons for teachers' involvement in teaching tasks , pt autonomous motivation applies to the teaching profession. Simply put, autonomously motivated teachers do their work because they enjoy teaching and find it meaningful. Results from our two studies suggest that teacher depersonalization is associated with students' lack of cooperation and can be prevented by school environments that provide supportive relationships to teachers. More importantly, the results highlight the importance of teachers' intrinsic orientation for teaching when explaining why depersonalization is associated with classroom behavior and developing strategies to prevent it.

10. Consequences of Depersonalization

Despite decades of research on teacher burnout and the theoretical underpinnings for predicting that burnout in general, or more specifically, depersonalization, has consequences for the behavior of teachers and students in the classroom, surprisingly little research has explored this topic. In the last two exceptions, no study to date has examined both teachers and students simultaneously , with depersonalization being associated with less effective teaching (Soenens et al., 2012) and less adaptive student motivation (Shen et al., 2015). Consistent with the evidence that students determine teachers' feelings and attitudes towards them, including teachers' self-depersonalization (Evers et al., 2004), it is no accident that it was concluded that teacher desensitization would be associated with a lower teacher's enthusiasm for teaching; In turn, it can be associated with students' disruption of the teacher's lessons.

The term interest can describe two different (often co-occurring) experiences: an individual's immediate experience of being fascinated by an object, as well as more persistent feelings that the object is enjoyable and worth further exploration. Thus, interest is both a psychological state characterized by increased attention, effort, and affect experienced at a given moment (situational interest), and a persistent disposition to re-engage with a particular object or subject over time (individual interest; Hidi & Renninger , 2006).

This dichotomy not only highlights the richness of the concept of increased interest, but also adds to the complexity of fully defining interest. It combines affective qualities such as situational interest, enjoyment, and excitement with cognitive qualities such as focused attention and perceived value, all of which are fed by the characteristics of the situation (Hidi & Renninger , 2006). For example, a student might enjoy a fun lesson about tsunamis , be impressed by their power, participate more in the lesson, and appreciate the personal relevance of the topic. Thus, being in a state of attention means that affective responses, perceived value and cognitive functioning are intertwined, attention and learning feel effortless (Ainley , 2006; Dewey , 1913; Hidi , 2006). Situational interest is about self-regulation, commitment to task, and persistence (Sansone & Thoman , 2005; Smith, Wagaman & Handley , 2009; Thoman , Smith & Silvia , 2011).

11. Situational Interest

Experiencing situational interest can directly promote learning by increasing attention and engagement. A student who sees a painting by Monet for the first time in an art history class may be attracted to bright colors and unusual brushstrokes, resulting in greater attention and deeper engagement. If this interest turns into an individual interest, the student will re-engage with the material overtime and explore the topic further (Harackiewicz , Durik , Barron , Linnenbrink -Garcia , & Tauer , 2008). It therefore predicts traditional measures of educational success, including interest, future course taking and performance.

Individual attention emphasizes individuals' stable preferences for certain content. Here, the experience of immediate attention reflects a well-developed personal preference for enjoying and valuing a particular subject or activity across situations. Self-interest is therefore a stable, underlying disposition that is set in motion in certain situations. For example, students interested in geophysics may be particularly likely to be interested during a lecture on earthquakes, whether the lesson is fun or not, because their interest is more developed and less dependent on situational factors.

12. Situational Interest and Individual Interest

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The four-stage model of interest development (Hidi and Renninger , 2006; Renninger and Hidi , 2016) integrates these two perspectives and their development:

- a. *Certain situations trigger interest, which can later develop between situations and become more persistent over time.*
- b. *First, features of the environment (e.g., novelty, uncertainty, surprise) attract one's attention.*
- c. *This situational interest may last longer beyond a single situation if the tasks seem meaningful and inclusive (ie, if the student perceives the task as valuable or enjoyable).*
- d. *Over time, repeated experiences of situational interest that are triggered and sustained can develop into an emerging individual interest such that the individual seeks opportunities to reconnect with the object.*
- e. *For example, if the student who at first admires Monet 's painting also enjoys the teacher's lecture on the Impressionist movement and then notices and appreciates the reproductions of Monet displayed in the dentist's office , the student might Google Monet 's images and order his biography.*
- f. *Finally, this emerging individual interest can develop into a self-sustaining, well-developed individual interest (for example, the student visits art museums and art history departments).*

13. Conclusion and Recommendations

Developing interest should not be an afterthought for the typical learning situation: Interest is essential to academic success. Interventions to develop student interest are important in any educational context but may be needed most in academic areas that most students initially found uninteresting, or in areas where interest typically declines over time. For example, in middle and high school, students' academic interest declines, particularly in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) (Brophy , 2008; Eccles et al., 1993). Educational psychology offers valuable insight into how people learn and plays a significant role in informing educational strategies and teaching methods. In addition to exploring the learning

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process itself, different areas of educational psychology explore the emotional, social, and cognitive factors that can affect how people learn. Topics such as special education, curriculum design, and educational technology require more valid curricula in educational psychology.

14. Source

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